

Analyzing South Sudan's Talent Pipeline Gap and Its Impact on Youth Employment and Labour Market Demand

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21177728>

Version: 1.0

March 2026

Abstract

South Sudan faces the highest youth unemployment rates in the world, with about 90% of youth reported to lack formal employment. Despite a growing number of graduates in technical and social fields, employers have failed to source talent for hire. This is largely due to a growing mismatch between the skills acquired in academia and the competencies required in the labour market. This study examined the structural and systemic factors that shape South Sudan's talent pipeline gap. The study particularly focused on training systems, digital skill readiness, and employer expectations. Using an explanatory sequential mixed-methods approach, this study examined the alignment between youth skills and labour-market demand. The study collected data through surveys, focus group discussions, and interviews with policymakers, educators, and labour market stakeholders in Juba. The study's findings revealed systemic bottlenecks in South Sudan's education and employment ecosystem. The study insights will be used to recommend evidence-based models for implementation to strengthen youth employability and address the skills mismatch, supporting the national goal of equipping youth with high-demand skills in the labour market by 2030 and the overall national development agenda.

Keywords: Digital skills, Educational outcomes, Labor market demands, Skills mismatch, Talent pipeline gap, Youth unemployment.

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AfDB – African Development Bank

ALU – African Leadership University

ICT – Information and Communication Technology

HCT - Human Capital Theory

HR - Human Resources

ILO – International Labour Organization

MIS – Management Information System

MoGEI – Ministry of General Education and Instruction

MoL – Ministry of Labour

MOu - Memorandum of Understanding

NGO – Non-Governmental Organization

NLP – National Labour Portal

OJT – On-the-Job Training

R-ARCSS – Revitalized Agreement on the Resolution of the Conflict in South Sudan

SDGs – Sustainable Development Goals

TVET – Technical and Vocational Education and Training

UN – United Nations

UNDP – United Nations Development Programme

UNESCO – United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization

VCT – Vocational Training Centre

VTL – Vocational Training Levy

1. Introduction

Youth unemployment is a structural socio-economic crisis in South Sudan exacerbated by years of conflict, weak institutional structures, and a stagnant private sector. Despite expanded access to basic and secondary education over the years, higher education remains out of reach for many, leaving the labour market with a limited absorptive workforce. “A recent study placed South Sudan among the countries with the lowest level of productive employment opportunity in Sub-Saharan Africa, with profound implications for stability, human capital formation, and national development (World Bank, 2023).”

A growing number of scholarly studies have linked rampant youth unemployment in conflict-affected areas to three recurrent “structural factors— skills mismatch, inadequate training ecosystems, and weak linkages between formal education and labour market needs (Kim & Tamborini, 2019).

This study examined skills mismatch and structural and systemic barriers that limit graduates from transitioning into meaningful employment.

1.1 Background to the Study

1.1.1 Historical Background

Decades of civil war and mass displacement have shaped South Sudan’s labor and education system. Before secession from Sudan, Southern Sudan suffered from mass marginalization, with minimal educational infrastructure and low human capital accumulation. Post-independence optimism was quickly undermined by renewed conflict in 2013 and 2016, which severely disrupted schooling, destroyed training institutions, and displaced over 4 million people internally and externally (UNDP, 2021). After the signing of the R-ARCSS in 2018, the country saw a modest gain in terms of enrollment.” “However, rampant corruption has left the education sector severely underfunded with insufficient teacher capacity, inadequate learning resources, and limited pathways to market-relevant skills formation (UNESCO, 2022).”

The private sector remains constrained by political instability, insecurity, and statutory barriers, leading to few opportunities for wage employment (AfDB, 2022). These structural factors have led to a disconnect between educational expansion and the capacity for economic absorption. “South Sudan youth comprise 74 percent of the population (UNDP,

2021)”, yet employment opportunities remain very scarce.

1.1.2 Theoretical Background

This study uses two theories to explain in detail the disconnect between educational training and employment outcomes.

Human Capital Theory

The Human Capital Theory states that investing in skill training, particularly through formal education, enhances productivity and positive labour market outcomes. However, in fragile contexts such as South Sudan, where factors like weak institutional structures, labour demand, and economic diversification are deficient, these positive returns weaken. The Human Capital theory helps explain why the modest growth in enrollment rates in South Sudan does not directly translate to employment. The system produces credentials; however, they do not align with the competencies required in the labour industry.

Skills Mismatch Theory

“In very general terms, skill (or qualification) mismatch is constructed by comparing the skills (or qualifications) of an employed worker with the skill (or qualification) requirements of her job (hence, the non-employed and the vacant jobs are largely disregarded) (Pellizzari & Fichen, 2017).” Qualification mismatch is the mismatch between a worker's formal education level and the job requirements, while skills mismatch is the mismatch between a worker's skills and the job requirements. A worker can be well-qualified but still under-skilled, or under-qualified but adequately skilled, depending on the job. The skills mismatch theory examines the misalignment between the skills job seekers possess and those required for the job.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

South Sudan’s labor market faces chronic deficits in industry-relevant skills, particularly in digital literacy, an essential skill in navigating today’s modern workforce (Jawad et al., 2024). With a fragmented, inadequately financed education system that is not aligned with labour market needs, and a lack of a functional Labour Market Information System (LMIS), South Sudan lacks a feedback loop between employers and educators, which widens the talent pipeline gap, hindering productivity and youth employability.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 General Objective

“To analyze the structural and systemic factors contributing to the mismatch between youth skills and labour market demands in South Sudan.”

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. To identify structural barriers that exacerbate youth unemployment and the limited talent pipeline in South Sudan.
2. To evaluate the efficacy of current vocational and professional training programs in enhancing the employability of young people.
3. To propose evidence-based strategies for integrating education-to-employment pathways that foster both formal employment and entrepreneurship.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What systemic and structural factors widen the gap between youth skills and market labor opportunities in South Sudan?
2. To what extent do current VCT and professional training programs align youth skills with labor market requirements?
3. What sustainable frameworks can address the gap between educational outcomes and labor market needs?

1.5 Hypotheses

H1: Skills mismatch is a major factor in the youth unemployment crisis in South Sudan.

H2: Existing vocational training programs and formal education fail to enhance youth employability due to a weak alignment with labour market demands.

H3: Integrated education-to-work pathways are perceived by youth as the primary requirement for closing the talent gap.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study addresses research gaps important to the national development of a skilled youth force by 2030. It serves as a source of reference for various bodies. The findings provide government and policymakers with empirical evidence to inform education reforms, workforce development, and youth employment policies. Training institutions can leverage the findings to align their curricula with labor market needs. Private sector employers gain a better understanding of workforce readiness. Development NGOs acquire empirical evidence essential in designing strong interventions in addressing youth unemployment. Scholars and researchers benefit from accessing critical reference sources for advancing research on youth employment in fragile contexts. The youth benefit from understanding the labor market and the bottlenecks that hinder their employment.

1.7 Scope of the Study

1.7.1 Content Scope

This study focuses on skills mismatch, training effectiveness, labour market demand, and youth employment outcomes.

1.7.2 Geographical Scope

This study was conducted in the capital, Juba, which is the country's main economic centre. Juba has a high concentration of post-secondary education institutions, a large youth population from diverse social and economic backgrounds, and a relatively high employer presence. Accessibility and strategic location make Juba the perfect location for this study.

1.7.3 Time Scope

This was covered in a period of 3 months, from January 2026 to March 2026, and investigated the training and education structures and training dynamics in South Sudan from 2015-2025, capturing a decade of post-conflict transformation.

1.8 Definition of Key Terms

Skills Mismatch – “Skill mismatch relates to the incongruity between the skills possessed by an individual and the skills demanded by their job or the broader labour market (Patel, 2025).”

Talent Pipeline – “A talent pipeline is defined as a ready supply of qualified people who meet the skill and competency requirements of an organization.

Youth Unemployment – Youth unemployment is the inability of individuals aged 18-35 to find formal or productive work when they are willing and able to work.

Labour Market Demand – “Labour market demand can be defined as the number of workers that an employer is willing and able to hire at a specific wage within a given time frame.

1.9 Summary

For a country recovering from decades of civil war amidst political instability and economic regression, youth unemployment remained a critical development challenge in South Sudan. This challenge was largely exacerbated by a structural mismatch between the skills young people possessed and those demanded by the labour market. Despite improvements in national basic and secondary education, youth still lacked the practical and technical skills needed for productive employment.

The national context, characterised by underfunded educational systems, outdated curricula, a weak link between institutional training and employers, and a lack of a national Labour Market Information System (LMIS), continued to widen this gap.

This research was anchored on two theoretical backgrounds: the Human Capital Theory and the Skills Mismatch Theory. The Human Capital Theory explains how investing in education can enhance individual productivity and economic outcomes, which is why there is a need for market-aligned skills. The Skills Mismatch theory highlights how the mismatch between educational outcomes and labour market needs leads to unemployment, underemployment, and low productivity.

This study sought to address this gap by examining the alignment between youth skills and labour market demands, particularly focusing on TVET and other training institutions.

2. Literature Review

The literature review synthesized contemporary research on skills mismatch, youth unemployment, and labour market dynamics in fragile-state contexts, with the focus narrowed down to sub-Saharan Africa. This review prioritized peer-reviewed publications and authoritative institutional reports published within the last 5 years. This chapter followed a method-driven layout in four sections: the conceptual framework, theoretical review, empirical review, and research gaps.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework in this study explained the interrelationships among skills mismatch, training program effectiveness, labour market demand, and youth employment outcomes.

2.1.1 Core Constructs

Table 1: *Operational Definitions of Core Research Constructs*

	Construct	Explanation
1.	Skills Mismatch	The divergence between the skills that job seekers possess and those demanded/needed by employers.
2.	Training Program Effectiveness	The measure of how a training program, be it vocational or professional training, achieves its intended goal of translating into market-relevant competencies or employment outcomes
3.	Labour Market Demands	The total demand for labour across a particular sector or even an economy. In simple terms, it is the number of jobs needed or demanded at a select time in an economy.
4.	Youth Employment Outcomes	The results of interventions that affect a young person's ability to find a job are measured through job placement, income generation, and job

		security.
5.	Institutional and Governance Factors	Variables that influence how education systems respond to market signals. They can either be regulatory, coordination, or capacity-related.

2.1.2 Conceptual Logic Model

1. Weak institutional capacity → outdated curricula → skills mismatch
2. Mismatch + limited employer engagement → low employability
3. Effective training + strong employer alignment → increased youth employment
4. labour market demand moderates the extent to which skills translate into jobs

This conceptual framework integrates both traditional and contemporary ideas on employment in fragile contexts. Young people get better job outcomes when the system is connected to the government, training centers, and employers.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the South Sudanese Talent Pipeline Gap

2.2 Theoretical Review

This study was grounded in two theoretical models: Human Capital Theory and Skills

Mismatch Theory. The review situates them within contemporary debates on labour development in fragile and post-conflict states.

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory

The idea behind human capital theory is that education is like an investment in that it yields future returns, and that its rate of return can be compared with other investments (Leoni, 2023). The accumulation of human capital does not necessarily translate to favorable employment outcomes if the market does not have the capacity to absorb it or when training outcomes do not align with economic needs. Scholarly research in the sub-Saharan African region posits that the return on education is dependent on factors such as institutional stability, private sector development, and the quality and relevance of training systems.

2.2.2 Skills Mismatch Theory

“Skills mismatch implies a discrepancy between the skills of job candidates or employed workers and job requirements. (Maltseva & Vera, 2019). Skill mismatch is a prevalent challenge in low-income countries, and this is highly attributed to the fact that most training systems in developing countries operate in isolation from labour market needs. For individuals, not having ‘the right skills’ limits employability prospects and access to quality jobs (Brunello & Wruuck, 2021). Long-term mismatch discourages job search and leads to long-term unemployment risk for youth.

2.2.3 Synthesis of Theories

This study integrates the Human Capital Theory (HCT) and Skills Mismatch Theory to understand educational training and labor market outcomes in fragile states. While HCT assumes a perfectly functioning market, the Skills Mismatch Theory is employed to address the structural realities of post-conflict systems. Combining these theories gives the study a triangulation, using numerical patterns (HCT) and contextual insights (Skills Mismatch Theory) to form a comprehensive picture of labor development.

2.3 Empirical Review

This section analyzed empirical literature on skills mismatch, youth unemployment, TVET effectiveness, and labour market dynamics in fragile and low-income contexts.

2.3.1 Skills Mismatch and Labour Market Outcomes

“High and persistent levels of unemployment, together with job vacancies that remain unfilled, are often attributed to mismatches between jobs and skills (ILO, 2019).” Scholars argue that the incidence of mismatch—manifesting as under-skilling, overskilling, or horizontal mismatch— has substantially increased in the past decade, mainly due to the rapid adoption of technology that is not proportionate to the slow curriculum modernization. Their analysis reveals that skills mismatch affects productivity, wages, and job stability, resulting in long-term unemployment challenges in low-income and fragile economies.

Although South Sudan is underrepresented in the dataset, the structural patterns analyzed are parallel to those of other fragile states. Patterns like weak institutions, a stagnant private sector, and insufficient infrastructure indicate potential relevance to South Sudan. ILO finds that the lack of a structured coordination system between the government, training institutions, and employers contributes to persistent competency deficits among graduates.

In East African labour markets, Nkwake and Atim (2022) report that youth typically lack foundational competencies in problem-solving, teamwork, and digital literacy, despite formal schooling attainment. This revelation reiterates the argument that formal education does not translate into market readiness in contexts where institutions are weak, underfunded, and the curricula do not align with evolving market needs.

2.3.2 TVET Effectiveness and Alignment With Labor Market Demands

A substantial body of recent research on TVET has underscored the importance of updating curriculum to stay relevant, instructor capacity building, and industry engagement. Studies have revealed that labour-market-oriented TVET systems generate significantly high employability outcomes, and this is driven by their focus on work-based learning and industry partnerships. “As economies become increasingly reliant on technology, the integration of AI into TVET curricula is essential to prepare a workforce capable of meeting the demands of a rapidly changing job market (Pavlova, 2014).”

Boateng and Amedahe (2022) further argue that most TVET institutions operate with outdated and inadequate equipment, which weakens their capacity to prepare students for digital sectors. This problem intensifies further in fragile contexts where there is limited investment and also high corruption.

In another study, Maringe et al. (2021) report that TVET programs only lead to positive employment outcomes when there is strong institutional governance and the labour market feedback loops. This reiterates the point that South Sudan’s lack of an LMIS reduces the nation's ability to adapt its curricula to emerging skill needs. Comparative studies from Kenya and Uganda, which are structurally and contextually similar to South Sudan, suggest that students enrolled in contemporary competency-based TVET programs are more likely to transition to formal employment. These findings reiterate the hypothesis that reforms in structures and systems towards competency-based models are crucial for talent pipelines in post-conflict labour markets.

2.3.3 Youth Unemployment in Fragile and Post-Conflict States

“Despite the effort to address the subject of youth unemployment and political instability separately, efforts made to examine the effect of youth unemployment and political instability in IGAD countries are very scanty (Hailu, 2022).” Recent studies show that political instability and weak institutional governance undermine youth employability. Evidence reveals that young people experience challenges in the labour market during and after conflict. This is largely due to the disruption of economic activities, the disruption of education, the destruction of infrastructure, and reduced investments.

A study by Walther and Frick (2021) found that youth from post-conflict nations struggle to transition to formal employment largely due to limited pathways that link education to work. Walter and Frick argue that rapid population growth under political instability and weak institutions intensifies the unemployment crisis, and this revelation is directly relevant to South Sudan.

Further to that, a recent report by the African Development Bank (AfDB, 2022) reveals that the youth unemployment rate across fragile states in Africa exceeds 60%. Furthermore, the report states that these critical numbers are exacerbated by a deficit in digital skills, a weak entrepreneurial ecosystem, and industrial diversification.

Figure 2: *Global Youth Unemployment Rates by Country (2022)*

Youth Unemployment by Country (2022)

Created by genuine impact

Youth unemployment refers to the share of the labor force ages 15-24 without work but available for and seeking employment. Djibouti has the highest youth unemployment rate in the world at almost 80%, while Qatar has the lowest at only 0.3%.

Countries greyed out have no available data.
More charts: genuineimpact.substack.com

Source: The World Bank

Source: The World Bank

2.3.4 Digital Skills and Employability in Sub-Saharan Africa

The global digital transformation has magnified the importance of ICT skills in the labour market. A systematic review by Ajani et al. (2023) reveals that digital skills are a major determinant of youth employability across Sub-Saharan Africa. “Given the bulging youth population in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), it stands to reason that the youth labour markets are affected most by these technological advancements, and that this is where governments and other stakeholders should focus their attention (Dinika, 2023).” The review concludes that digital literacy contributes to a better education-to-employment relation, resulting in improved employability outcomes.

Digital skills acquisition also correlates with entrepreneurial success. Youth with ICT proficiency are likely to identify capacity building resources online, explore online market opportunities, and engage in digital gig work. These capacities can support South Sudan's constrained job market. Cross-country studies by Furuholt and Kristiansen (2021) reveal that digital infrastructure in fragile states limits youth potential to delve into digital forms of employment or seek opportunities beyond their borders. This reveals a critical revelation that South Sudan's education system fails to provide digital competencies that support emerging labour markets.

2.3.5 Institutional Capacity, Governance, and Labour Market Systems

Throughout the history of labour economics, in almost all nations, labour market institutions and policies have crucially impacted the changing pattern of unemployment. In general, labour market institutions and policies are essential for shaping the employment realm globally (Giotis, 2024). Giotis argues that governance deficits limit the effectiveness of youth employment programs through corruption and embezzlement, lack of transparency and accountability, and underfunding. These findings are visibly evident structural weakness in South Sudan's TVET sector.

Le Petit-Guerin (2024) further emphasizes the lack of a functional Labour Market Information System (LMIS) as a big contributor to a failed talent pipeline. The report's analysis shows that weak institutions and governance cannot produce talent to match supply with demand effectively.

Conclusively, a report from the World Bank (2023) indicates that post-conflict zones with weak or no LMIS infrastructure do not invest in skills training infrastructure, and this leads to information asymmetry between youth, trainers, and employers.

2.4 Identification of Research Gaps

Despite extensive literature on skills mismatch and youth unemployment in Africa, the following gaps remain:

Table 2: *Summary of Identified Research Gaps in Literature*

	Research Gap	Description / Evidence
1.	Lack of Empirical Studies Focused on South Sudan	While peer-reviewed studies exist on the study topic, there are no recent ones that are specifically focused on South Sudan's talent pipeline dynamics, TVET performance, or employer skill demand.
2.	Limited Integration of Multi-Stakeholder Perspectives	Existing and accessible studies rarely combine data from all variables of the study. The studies do not combine data from youth, employers, policymakers, and training institutions. The failure to use this approach makes it hard to understand systemic misalignment, as all stakeholders are equally important in arriving at the problem definition.
3.	Absence of Research on Digital Skills Readiness in Post-Conflict Contexts	Research in fragile environments is steadily growing; however, there is limited literature on digital skills and infrastructure deficits in post-conflict and conflict contexts.
4.	Weak Evidence on TVET Impact in Fragile States	Most TVET research in sub-Saharan Africa focuses on more stable economies like Kenya, Ghana, and South Africa. Conflicted and post-conflict states remain understudied, and that makes it hard to rely on that research, as there is a big technological and governance gap between those states.
5.	Lack of Labour Market Information System (LMIS) Analyses	There is no empirical assessment of how the absence of an LMIS in South Sudan and similar post-conflict and unstable economies affects curriculum design, employer engagement, or youth transitions.

2.5 Summary

The literature review examined existing research on skills mismatch, youth unemployment, and labour market systems in fragile states, particularly focusing on sub-Saharan Africa and

other developing countries in the Global South. The chapter restated the key concepts used in this study, outlined the theories that guide this study, and examined recent empirical findings on TVET performance, employer expectations, and youth employment outcomes. The review shows a consistent problem: training systems in fragile states failed to align with market needs due to weak governance, outdated curricula, and lack of engagement with the employer (Brunello & Wruuck, 2021). The review also shows how digital skills have almost become a prerequisite for employment, yet many youth from low-income and post-conflict states have limited access (Ajani et al., 2023). Across the works reviewed, there are several gaps that were noted. There is no empirical research on South Sudan's labour market or the scale of its skills mismatch, there is no evidence on how training institutions in fragile contexts engage employers, and there are almost no studies on digital readiness in post-conflict zones. Some of the findings contradict each other; for example, TVET programs are reported to improve employment outcomes in some studies. In contrast, others argue that TVET programs have almost no impact in post-conflict zones where there is weak governance and no industry feedback loops. The highlighted uncertainties and contradictions justify the need to pursue this study and shape the methodological approach in the research methodology.

3. Methodology

The research methodology describes the research design and the methods used to study youth skills development, digital competence, and employment opportunities in Juba, South Sudan. This chapter outlines the research design, study population, sampling approach, data collection instruments, analysis procedures, and ethical considerations. This study examined both measurable patterns in youth employment and personal experiences of young people navigating both the formal training and labour market sectors.

This study explored the growing gap between the skills young people possessed and the skills demanded in South Sudan's labor market, with a specific focus on urban centres like Juba, the study area. Despite growing enrolment rates in post-secondary education, higher education, and VCT programs, many young people still struggle to transition into stable formal employment.

This study exclusively sought to examine how youth skills development, digital competence, and employment opportunities relate in Juba and across South Sudan. Consequently, the study would identify the structural, institutional, and individual barriers that influence youth participation in the labor market.

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What systemic and structural factors widen the gap between youth skills and market labor opportunities in South Sudan?
2. To what extent do current VCT and professional training programs align youth skills with labor market requirements?
3. What sustainable frameworks can address the gap between educational outcomes and labor market needs?

3.1 Research Philosophy

This research was based on a pragmatic research philosophy that emphasized the use of multiple methods to address complex research problems. Epistemologically, pragmatism is premised on the idea that research can steer clear of metaphysical debates about the nature of truth and reality and focus instead on 'practical understandings' of concrete, real-world issues (Kelly & Cordeiro, 2020).

The study used an inductive-deductive research approach. Deductive reasoning was used to analyze the quantitative survey data in order to acquire occurring patterns in skill levels and employment outcomes. In contrast, inductive reasoning was used in the qualitative analysis of the focus group discussions and interviews to identify trends in the training systems, labour market expectations, and structural barriers to employment.

3.2 Research Design

This study employed a sequential explanatory mixed-methods research design that combined quantitative and qualitative data approaches to capture both numerical patterns and contextual insights related to the study subject. According to Amina Ahmed et al. (2024), integrating both qualitative and quantitative data allows researchers to capture both the breadth of a phenomenon and the depth of human experience, leading to richer insights. The purpose of the second qualitative phase is often to explain the results discovered in the first quantitative phase, and sometimes to explain outliers that are not entirely consistent with the collected data (Toyon, 2021).

The quantitative survey provided the study with measurable insights into youth unemployment patterns, skills levels, and training experiences. The qualitative methods, focus group discussions, and semi-structured interviews then explained the patterns observed in the survey findings, from which contextual insights were derived from youth, policy, and market stakeholders.

The quantitative component of this research was a structured survey through Google Forms filled out by youth participants from Juba. The survey collected data on demographic characteristics, educational background, employment status, skill levels, and experiences related to internships or practical training. Collecting this data allowed the researcher to identify patterns in youth skills development and employment outcomes across South Sudan's capital.

The qualitative component of the data was conducted through two methods: focus group discussions (FGDs) with TVET and university students and recent graduates within the last five years, and semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders in the education, formal training, policy, and labour sectors. The focus group discussions were centred on experiences of young people in education, training programs, and job search. The semi-structured interviews collected the perspectives of employers, TVET trainers, administrators, and policymakers. These interviews were based on identifying the challenges or gaps within

training institutions as well as labour market needs and expectations. Opting for quantitative data alone would not be able to fully explain the structural barriers and institutional limitations that affect youth employment. Integrating both quantitative and qualitative data provided both statistical evidence and contextual understanding.

3.3 Participants & Setting

3.3.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Juba, the capital city of South Sudan. Juba is the largest and most populous town in the country. It serves as the political, administrative, and economic center of the country, hosting major government offices, international organizations, educational institutions, and private sector businesses, which positions it in an influential role in shaping employment opportunities for young people and the labour market ecosystem, making it contextually relevant for examining the relationship between youth skills development and labour market outcomes.

Figure 3: Map of the Study Area: Juba, South Sudan

Source: Adapted from pexels and edited on Canva

3.3.2 Research Population

The research population for this study focused primarily on young people living in Juba, particularly students in tertiary education or recent graduates transitioning from education or training into the labour market.

The study population included individuals from various academic and employment backgrounds, such as:

- university students and graduates
- vocational and technical trainees
- unemployed youth actively seeking work
- self-employed youth operating small businesses
- youth employed in either the formal or informal sectors

Additionally, the study also included key stakeholders in the labour market who influence the development and utilization of skills in the economy. Stakeholders involved included: employers, university lecturers, TVET trainers, education administrators, and policymakers involved in workforce development initiatives.

3.3.3 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

The quantitative component of the study, which was administered through a Google Forms survey, included 161 youth respondents. The survey participants were selected using a convenience sampling method, reached through available networks, educational institutions, and online communication platforms. Although the convenience sampling method limits the statistical generalizability of the findings in the study area, it enabled the researcher to collect useful insights from a diverse participant population across educational backgrounds, employment status, and training experiences within the employment landscape in Juba, within the timeline of the research.

The appropriate sample was determined using Cochran's formula. This formula calculates the minimum required sample size for a large population at a specified confidence level and margin of error:

Where:

n_0 = minimum required sample size

Z = Z-score for 95% confidence level (1.96)

p = estimated proportion with the attribute (0.5, used to maximize sample size)

$q = 1 - p$

e = margin of error (0.05 for $\pm 5\%$)

Calculation for this study

$$n_0 = Z^2pq / e^2 = (1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5) / (0.05)^2 = 0.9604 / 0.0025 \approx 384.16 \approx 385$$

Since the estimated youth population in Juba is finite, a finite population correction (FPC) can be applied:

$$n = n_0 / (1 + (n_0 - 1)/N)$$

Substituting the values ($n_0 = 384$, $N = 532,000$):

$$n = 384 / (1 + (384 - 1)/532,000) = 384 / (1 + 0.00072) \approx 383.7$$

Note: Although the sample of 161 is well below the Cochran-calculated ideal of 385, it maintains a 95% confidence level, with a revised margin of error of $\pm 7.72\%$. While not sufficient for high-precision point estimates, the sample is still suitable for identifying trends in the study subject. This reduction in statistical power was compensated for by a subgroup analysis where a triangulation approach was taken with the KIIs and FGDs to provide qualitative depth where quantitative precision was limited by the sample size.

For the qualitative aspect of this study, the researcher opted for purposive sampling to select participants for focus group discussions. Focus group participants were selected from TVET and youth associations in the capital. The respondents came from different educational and professional backgrounds to allow a diverse perspective on the findings of the study. There were 3 focus group discussions (FGDs) consisting of 6, 8, and 11 youths, each falling under either of these categories: graduates, unemployed, or TVET attendees. The participants were selected from both private and public institutions so that the study reflects a general landscape from both fields. Their responses were briefly summarized to capture varied perspectives.

The KIIs participants were selected using a snowball sampling technique. The researcher initiated the interviews with known contacts and eventually transitioned to referrals to other persons relevant to the study. The primary interviews were held with stakeholders from the private sector— particularly startups adapting digital technologies in their work, training institutions, administrators, and officials involved in formulating or implementing policies around education and employment. The qualitative component included 9 Key Informant Interviews with university lecturers, TVET trainers, administrators, employers, and policymakers, selected across various sectors, including formal employment, informal

enterprises, and SMEs, to capture diversity on the demand side. Each interview followed a semi-structured format while allowing flexibility for participants to elaborate on their experiences, and responses were documented in written notes. The interview notes were later reviewed and organized into key thematic categories.

3.4 Instrumentation

3.4.1 Operationalization of Key Variables

To ensure clarity in measurement, the key variables in this study were operationalized as follows:

Table 3: Operationalization of Research Variables

Variable	Definition / Measurement	Data Source	Link to Objective
Digital Skills	Self-reported proficiency in technical and digital skills.	Survey & FGDs	Objective 1: Assess skill mismatch and digital competence
Employment Status	Categorized as unemployed, self-employed, formally employed, or a student.	Survey	Objective 2: Examine youth labor market positioning
Skill Mismatch	Comparison between respondents' educational background/training and current job requirements, including perceived competency gaps	Survey, FGDs & Interviews	Objective 1: Identify gaps in skills vs. employment needs
Access to Training Opportunities	Availability, frequency, and perceived quality of formal, technical, and vocational training programs	Survey & FGDs	Objective 2: Evaluate accessibility of training programs

Barriers to Employment	Obstacles to employment, including lack of experience, limited networks, gender disparities, and institutional constraints	Survey, FGDs & Interviews	Objective 3: Identify structural and personal barriers to employment
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By operationalizing these variables, the researcher was able to analyze the survey data, FGDs, and KIIs, using a clear framework that ensured consistency in interpreting both quantitative and qualitative findings.

3.4.2 Data Collection Instruments

The data used in this study were collected through three instruments.

The first instrument was a structured digital survey questionnaire titled *Youth Employment and Skills Survey*, administered through Google Forms. The questionnaire was captured primarily with closed-ended questions, multiple-choice items, and a Likert scale. The questionnaire was structured into five sections. The first section introduced the study, section two captured demographics, section four examined the participants' experiences with employment, and the final section explored barriers to employment and the support respondents believed would be essential in boosting their employability.

The second instrument was Focus Group Discussions, which was a guided, structured conversation meant to facilitate feedback from youth participants. The data was collected through open-ended questions designed to encourage the FGD participants to share their lived experiences with education, training programs, job searching, and their perceptions of employability, constraints, coping strategies, and entrepreneurship prospects.

The third instrument was a semi-structured interview guide, used to conduct interviews with employers, trainers, administrators, and policymakers. The interview questions focused on gaps in the labour markets, skills needed, talent pipeline, expectations of employers, training quality, labour demand, institutional constraints, challenges that educators and administrators face in adapting education and training systems to labor market requirements, and possible improvements.

3.4.3 Pilot Testing of Research Instruments

Before proceeding to collect the main data for the researcher, the digital questionnaire was pilot tested within a small group of students who shared similar characteristics with the target population. Pilot acts as a guardian against possible hazards by revealing hidden problems early on, greatly lowering the likelihood of experiencing substantial setbacks during full-scale implementation (Renuse & Ijmrr Analytics, 2024). Feedback from the pilot participants was used to identify and improve minor errors like numbering and spelling. All questions were revised once more to improve clarity and reduce potential ambiguity. The pilot testing, therefore, played a major role in strengthening the quality and reliability of the data collection tools used in this study.

3.5 Procedures

3.5.1 Data Collection Procedures

The data in this study were collected through two complementary stages.

Quantitative data were collected through a survey questionnaire distributed electronically to youth participants using online platforms and communications networks. The form was distributed to participants in Juba who were willing to participate voluntarily, without compensation, and were required to submit a consent form before participating. The results were documented through Google Sheets.

To complement the survey findings, the qualitative data were collected through three focus group discussions with selected youth participant groups. The discussions provided the participants with the opportunity to reflect on their experiences and challenges. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with key stakeholders involved in youth employment and training systems.

3.5.2 Ethical Considerations

The researcher applied for ethics approval from the university before collecting data. Throughout the data collection process, all ethical principles in line with ALU's data collection ethics were followed. The researcher ensured that the whole process did not bring any harm to participants and ensured that their dignity and privacy were upheld. Before proceeding with filling out the survey questionnaires, the participants read through their rights and what the study was about. They were informed that participation was voluntary and they could withdraw at any stage of the process, and that the data collected was meant for

research purposes only. The form did not collect emails, names, or any personal identifying information. The questionnaire was administered strictly to participants aged 18 and above, as minors are not in a position to provide informed consent. During the FGDs and KIIS, no photographs or audio recordings were taken in accordance with the participants' preferences. All data was documented through handwritten notes. All collected data were stored securely and will be destroyed 6 months from the onset of this study.

3.5.3 Data Analysis

The research objectives were reviewed to ensure that the analytical procedure aligned with the purpose of the study. The quantitative survey data were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques like frequency distributions, percentages, and mean scores. These techniques grouped the data in demographic characteristics, levels of digital skills, employment status, and perceived barriers to employment. The study used Google Sheets to process statistical calculations, with the findings visualized on charts and graphs to illustrate key patterns in the data. The qualitative data from the FGDS and KIIs were analyzed using thematic analysis. According to Sirwan Ahmed et al. (2025), thematic analysis provides a structured yet flexible method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns in qualitative data. This process involved four steps. First, the researcher reviewed the written notes from the discussions and interviews to familiarize himself with the data. Second, recurring ideas were coded into preliminary categories, and later thematically developed into broader themes that represented key issues in training, skill gaps, barriers to employment, and labor market needs. Lastly, the thematic categories were then interpreted to comprehensively explain the findings and patterns that were observed from the quantitative survey data.

3.6 Quality & Constraints

3.6.1 Validity and Reliability of Data

To ensure the validity of the collected data, the survey questionnaire was developed along thematic lines identified in the literature review. The questionnaire was structured in 5 sections as explained in section 3.3.2. The questions from the focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews also followed the same thematic lines. The structured approach helped to ensure that the questions were directly related to the objectives of the study. To ensure reliability, each data collection tool used uniform questions and predefined response

options (particularly the questionnaire) to ensure consistency. Using clearly defined rating scales reduced ambiguity. The procedures contributed to the overall validity and reliability of the survey data.

3.6.2 Assumptions of the Study

This study was conducted based on several assumptions. The study assumed that the respondents honestly and authentically responded to the survey, focus group discussions, and semi-structured interviews. Furthermore, the study assumed the participants had sufficient understanding and experience around the study topic and area. The study also assumed the data collection instruments covered the key variables related to youth skills development and employment outcomes.

3.6.3 Delimitations of the Study

Due to logistical constraints, the study was limited to youth residing in Juba. The study was also limited to youth above the age of 18 years for ethical compliance with informed consent. Additionally, the research focused specifically on the objective themes, rather than broader macroeconomic or national labour market policies.

3.6.4 Limitations of the Study

This study sought methodological rigor; however, a few limitations were encountered during the study. The study used convenience sampling due to time constraints. This limited the generalizability of the findings as the selection was based on accessibility and not random sampling. Second, the geographical limit of Juba provided valuable insights. Still, it could not fully represent the experiences of South Sudanese youth in other regions of the country where access to economic opportunities and training differs. The use of self-reported data through the digital questionnaire might lead respondents to provide responses that are viewed as desirable rather than reporting authentic experiences. Lastly, internet access and digital literacy influenced participation, which reduced the sample size and also potentially excluded other individuals. Despite these limitations, the structure of the data collection tools provided diverse and useful insights into youth skills development and employment challenges in the study area.

3.7 Summary

This chapter presented the methodology used to investigate the research questions. The study used a mixed-methods approach grounded in a pragmatic research philosophy, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to understand the research problem fully. This chapter described the study area, research population, sampling techniques, and the data collection instruments used in the study. It also outlined the data collection and analysis procedures, while emphasizing the use of descriptive statistics and thematic analysis for quantitative and qualitative data, respectively. The chapter finally addressed the ethical considerations, limitations, and measures taken to ensure validity and reliability.

4. Results and Findings

This chapter presents the study findings from the “Youth Employment Survey” ($n = 161$) and insights from the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and Informant interviews. The findings are analyzed thematically as shown in Figure 4, to evaluate the systemic bottlenecks in South Sudan’s education systems and talent pipeline. This chapter tests the hypothesis related to skills mismatch, institutional effectiveness, and the potential of integrated education-to-work pathways.

Figure 4: *Thematic Map of Qualitative Findings (Skill Gaps & Gatekeeping)*

4.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

4.1.1 Distribution of Respondents by Age and Gender

The demographic profile of the sample from the survey reflects a young male-leaning population. As shown in Figure 5, the majority (57.8%) of the respondents fall within the 23-27 age bracket, a concentration that shows an “early career” phase and gender disparities.

Figure 5: Gender Distribution Across Age Groups of Survey Respondents

Interpretation

The sample is dominated by “early career youth” as 88.9% of the respondents fall in the 18-27 age bracket. This concentration suggests barriers to entry-level employment. The gender is relatively balanced in the 18-22 age bracket, but the gap widens with a male domination in the 23-27 and 28-35 age brackets. This suggests that the talent pipeline narrows for young women as they progress to higher education and professional roles, potentially due to gender disparities in access to educational resources and cultural influences such as early marriage.

4.1.2 Educational Attainment and Confidence

To determine the relationship between academic background and career readiness, the study measured the respondents’ confidence in their skills across different educational qualifications. As shown in Table 4, higher levels of operational specialization corresponded with a greater sense of market readiness.

Table 4: Demographic Distribution: Age and Gender of Respondents

Education Level	Average (\bar{x}) Confidence Score
TVET / Vocational	4.33
Bachelor's Degree	4.21
Diploma	3.94
Secondary	3.70
Primary	2.00

Analysis

The analysis reveals a “Vocational Edge” where graduates from a TVET background report higher ($\bar{x} = 4.33$) employability confidence compared to Bachelor’s holders ($\bar{x} = 4.21$) and Diploma holders ($\bar{x} = 3.94$). These findings suggest Juba’s labor market gives more professional agency to discrete technical skills over theoretical degrees. While universities are theory-heavy, vocational training specializes in a narrow operational niche with practical marketable utility that bypasses the Experience Catch-22. Conversely, sharp drops of confidence in Secondary ($\bar{x} = 3.70$) and Primary ($\bar{x} = 2.00$) reveal a credential floor, where youth without specialized training are disconnected from the modern talent pipeline. These findings corroborate that specialization beats generalization: practical training prepares graduates to apply learning outcomes in real-world situations.

4.2 Labor Market Participation and Employment Status

To understand the absorptive capacity of Juba’s labor market, the respondents’ current employment status was recorded. As shown in Table 5, the majority of the respondents were students or unemployed, with just 13.7% falling in the formal workforce.

Table 5: *Employment Status Breakdown (n = 161)*

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Student / Trainee	66	41.0%
Unemployed	45	28.0%
Self-employed	22	13.7%
Employed (Formal)	22	13.7%
Employed (Informal)	6	3.7%

Analysis

The employment status numbers suggest a significant transition bottleneck. Students and unemployed youth account for 69% of the sample, with formal employment absorbing just 13.7% of the sample. These numbers suggest a high supply of graduates from training institutions, but the formal sector’s absorptive capacity is too small. It could also suggest that the supply of graduates lacks the key skills that formal employers seek. This revelation leaves a narrow pipe for the talent volume produced from training institutions.

4.3 Thematic Analysis of Qualitative Findings

While the survey provided quantitative breadth, the FGDs and KIIs provided qualitative depth. The qualitative data were thematically grouped into three themes. The thematic analysis of the qualitative findings identified three structural and systemic barriers that shrink South Sudan’s pipeline and limit the labor market’s absorptive capacity, as illustrated in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: *Thematic Map of Qualitative Findings: Core Barriers in the Talent Pipeline*

Source: Research Qualitative Data (FGDs and KIIs), 2026.

Note. Qualitative insights derived from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) conducted in Juba (2026).

Theme 1: The "Theory-Heavy" Curriculum Trap

The FGDs and KIIs consistently noted that higher education institutions across the country prioritize rote memorization with little to no market-applicable skills.

- FGDs Insight: “Over the four years of my undergraduate degree, the best students were those who memorized lectures. This doesn’t leave us with much time to explore self-taught skills as we continuously revise notes to keep them in mind.”
- Interview Insight: A senior employee from a UN Agency stated, *“More often, we have employed graduates with first-class degrees; however, they fail to deliver after orientation, some could barely draft a professional memo, while others struggle to manage a basic Excel budget. This has forced us to add practical assessment in our interviews.”*

Interpretation: This qualitative evidence reinforces the lower scores in "Technical" and "Digital" skills self-assessment from the survey, as illustrated in Section 4.4.

Theme 2: Systemic "Gatekeeping" and Lack of Information

FGDs participants expressed frustration over what they described as a “hidden job market” where access to opportunities is limited to a few individuals and their networks. This was further reinstated in an interview with an HR representative in a local marketing firm.

- FGD Insight: A young, frustrated graduate stated, *“In Juba, it is not about what you know, it is about who you know. If you don’t have an influential uncle in the system, you are not different from someone who has not gone to school, as the only jobs that don’t need connections are manual.”*
- Interview Insight: A HR manager from a local marketing firm said, *“Because of a lack of trust in the educational outcomes, hiring is no longer transparent, and we mostly rely on referrals to fill in open roles. This proves effective, but it also limits our access to talents with immense potential.”*

Interpretation: The Systemic Gatekeeping theme from the qualitative insights supports the quantitative findings on barriers to entry-level roles, where “Connections/Nepotism” and “Lack of Job Information” possessed the highest mentioned frequency, as illustrated in Figure 9.

Theme 3: The Digital Divide as a Barrier to Entry

A Key Informant from a training centre noted that youth across the capital are social media savvy. He noted the unprecedented growth of social media usage across the country, but highlighted how youth still struggle with professional digital literacy. Another point that was echoed across FGDs was that most of them only have access to smartphones, which limits them to navigate professional digital skills that would require a more advanced device like a tablet or personal computer. They also noted that Facebook offers a free version through MTN, while learning digital skills would require volumes of internet data, which is costly.

Interpretation: Theme three suggests a quantitative triangulation. In the skills competency self-assessment illustrated in Figure 7, digital and technical skills received lower averages compared to soft skills. This contributes to the theme “Digital divide as a barrier.”

4.4 Testing Hypothesis 1: The Skills Mismatch

H1: *Skills mismatch is a major factor in the youth unemployment crisis in South Sudan.*

To test this hypothesis, respondents rated their proficiency in five areas. As seen in Figure 7, the talent pipeline stretches in teamwork ($\bar{x} = 3.92$), communication ($\bar{x} = 3.69$), and problem-solving ($\bar{x} = 3.62$), but is pinched in technical ($\bar{x} = 3.34$) and digital skills ($\bar{x} = 3.30$). This indicates a “Soft Skill Surplus” but a “Technical Skill Deficit.” It shows that youth are theoretically prepared for work but lack key technical skills.

Figure 7: Mean (\bar{x}) Self-Rated Proficiency Across Core Skill Areas

Source: Youth Employment and Skills Survey (2026), $n = 161$.

Interpretation

These findings corroborate H1. The modern labor market is increasingly adopting digital tools to accelerate productivity, promote collaboration across teams, and archive assets. This has made digital literacy no longer an option. The lack of technical depth and digital proficiency creates a “competency gap”. The volume of talent is qualified on paper, but cannot efficiently work in an environment that adapts to rapidly evolving technology.

Qualitative Triangulation

A significant portion of FGDs participants stated that they easily navigated the initial review and interview stage of job applications, but could not pass the practical assessment. They stated they felt socially and theoretically ready, but technically handicapped. This dual evidence indicates that youth are not essentially unqualified, but the existence of a broader lack of alignment between what they are taught and what employers need.

4.5 Testing Hypothesis 2: Institutional and Training Effectiveness

H2: Existing vocational training programs and formal education fail to enhance youth employability due to a weak alignment with labour market demands.

To test hypothesis 2, the study examined youth perception of their readiness to apply their acquired skills in real-world settings. As shown in Figure 8, more than half of the respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the relevance of their training to current market demands.

Figure 8: *The Vocational Edge: Perceived Employability Confidence*

Interpretation

The data support H2. With 56.5% of the youth expressing they felt “partly” or “not at all” confident in the relevance of their training to what employers need, it is evident that the skills mismatch stems from an outdated curriculum that does not evolve at the speed of the labor market demands. This result can be termed as “qualified unemployment,” denoting that graduates possess certificates that are obsolete in the technologically-leaning industry.

Practical Learning Gap and Thematic Alignment

Qualitative data from a KII revealed that university curricula are “theory heavy,” prioritizing memorization over hands-on learning. This insight also mirrors the “Theory-Heavy” theme identified from FGDs, who blamed the skill gap on a lack of “funding for laboratories,” and “outdated textbooks”. These revelations reinforce that the mismatch is a result of systemic failure of the pipeline, rather than a lack of student effort.

4.6 Barriers to Entry

4.6.1 Systemic Gatekeeping and the Experience Catch-22

The analysis identified the primary hurdles preventing youth from moving from "trained" to "employed." As shown in Figure 9, the "Connections/Nepotism," “Lack of Job Information,” and “Lack of Experience” were moderately cited as barriers.

Figure 9: *Primary Barriers Preventing Employment Entry for Youth*

Interpretation.

While lack of jobs is relatively perceived as the highest barrier (81 mentions), the data also indicates that "Few job opportunities" (61 mentions), "connections/nepotism" (77 mentions), and "Lack of "Experience and Skills" (84 mentions) combined are major hurdles for youth, signaling "Systemic Gatekeeping" (Theme 2) and "The Experience Catch 22". This indicates that the pipeline is not only blocked by a skill mismatch but also by a pipeline that operates only through closed networks, hence blocking youth who possess the skills but lack the "social capital."

The thematic analysis suggests that the absence of a "transparent pipeline," facilitated by a lack of non-discriminative hiring policies, turns the talent pipeline into a "leaky pipe." This data also corroborates the " Experience Catch 22" where employers require youth to have some experience, but cannot gain that experience without landing a job. Without these bridges, graduates frequently fall into long-term unemployment immediately after completing their studies, as the pipeline does not facilitate transition.

4.6.2 The Psychological Toll of Searching

To assess how the pipeline bottleneck affects the sample psychologically, the study analyzed the relationship between participants' job search duration and level of confidence in their skills as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: *The Confidence Decay Model: Self-Efficacy over Search Time*

The Confidence Decay Model

Analysis

Figure 10 reveals a “Confidence Decay” with prolonged job search. In the first six months, the confidence level is very high.

The data reveals a "Confidence Decay" as job search duration increases. While 67% of respondents in the initial six months report high confidence, the ratio of "Low Confidence" individuals doubles among those searching for more than two years. This shift suggests that the "Experience Catch-22" does not just block employment; it actively erodes the professional identity and self-efficacy of youth over time, leading to labor market detachment.

4.7 Testing Hypothesis 3: The Integrated Pathway Solution

H3: *Integrated education-to-work pathways are perceived by youth as the primary requirement for closing the talent gap.*

To test Hypothesis 3, respondents were asked to identify interventions they believed would enhance their employability, as shown in Figure 11. The objective of this question was to determine whether youth prioritized traditional academic systems or modern, practical industry-linked pathways.

Figure 11: *Youth-prioritized interventions for enhancing employability (n = 161)*

Analysis

As illustrated in Figure 11, the results reveal a strong preference for practical experience and technical upskilling over standard classroom instruction. Internships and apprenticeships emerged as the top priority, cited by 29.8% of respondents, followed closely by digital skills programs at 27.3%. Notably, traditional training (general education) was prioritized by only 14.9% of the youth surveyed.

These findings provide empirical support for H3. The data suggests that youth in Juba recognize a "practicality gap" in their current qualifications. The high demand for internships—which bridge the gap between theory and practice—and digital skills—which

are often excluded from standard curricula—indicates that integrated pathways are perceived as the most viable solution to the talent gap. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the view that industry-integrated learning is a primary requirement for improving employment outcomes in South Sudan.

4.8 Summary

The findings in this chapter suggest a systemic failure in the talent pipeline. While the youth are pursuing education, the current system emphasizes theoretical knowledge over technical and digital competencies (H1). This is exacerbated by a training ecosystem that operates in isolation from the private sector (H2). However, the strong consensus on the need for internships and digital training suggests that adopting an integrated education-to-employment pathway (H3) could significantly improve labor market outcomes for the youth in Juba.

5. Discussion

This chapter puts together the study's empirical findings to address systemic barriers within Juba's talent pipeline. This section integrates survey data with qualitative insights from the FGDs and KIIs, exploring the theory-heavy curricula, the experience catch-22, and the digital divide. This section will propose actionable, evidence-based solutions to South Sudan's education-to-work crisis.

5.1 The "Theory-Heavy" Curriculum Trap (H1 & H2)

This study reveals a disconnect between education outcomes and labor market requirements. Higher Education students and graduates reported a system that prioritizes rote memorization and is centred on theoretical exams with little to no hands-on/ industry exposure. This finding reinforces Skills Mismatch Theory (Maltseva & Vera, 2019), which identifies a lack of compatibility between job requirements and a candidate's skills as the primary drivers of professional urgency. As identified earlier in the literature review, when the system prioritizes theoretical over practical learning, graduates enter the labor market with "paper qualifications" but lack the professional confidence to perform (World Bank, 2020).

Furthermore, this study reveals a different bottleneck for TVET participants, who possess hands-on technical knowledge but lack "Tool Capital". The Human Capital Theory (Leoni, 2023) suggests that education is an investment, and like other investments, it yields returns. This study, however, reveals a critical caveat in the context of South Sudan, where training in skills like mechanics and carpentry is redundant if the trainee cannot afford the basic equipment needed to start a business. South Sudan's talent is not only a technical skills deficiency but also a lack of physical capital that would facilitate the realization of the "returns" the Human Capital Theory promises.

5.2 The Experience "Catch-22" and Systemic Gatekeeping

The education-to-work pathway is blocked by a leaky pipe. The lack of experience traps youth in a "catch-22," where they can't get an entry-level job without prior experience. Still, they cannot gain that experience before they work, as the education-labor tunnel lacks transition bridges. This corroborates the argument made by Walyer and Frick (2021), who

asserted that youth from post-conflict and fragile states struggle to transition to decent work after graduation due to the absence of a formal pathway that links graduates to the workforce. Furthermore, close-ended, connection-based hiring creates a hidden job market. This finding contributes a local dimension to the foundational competency gap mentioned by Nkwake and Atim (2023), where they claim even when youth possess the required skills, systemic gatekeeping excludes them if they lack the social capital to navigate informal networks.

5.3 Digital Competence and the Infrastructure Barrier

While traditional hiring systems considered digital literacy an added advantage in employment prospects, it is a mandatory requirement in the modern labor market. While literature posits digital skills as a major determinant of employability in Sub-Saharan Africa (Ajani et al., 2023), the reality for South Sudanese youth is that this determinant is stifled by infrastructural barriers such as high internet costs and a lack of hardware. These findings align with Furuholt and Kristiansen (2021), who suggest that infrastructural deficits in post-conflict and fragile states/ economies significantly limit the potential for young people to transition into the global digital economy. Without addressing these infrastructural barriers, the “bulging youth population” mentioned by Dinika (2023) remains a missed economic opportunity for the country.

5.4 Informal Employment and Economic Fragility

Given the volume of graduates released into the workforce and the contrasting few that transition into employment, this study concludes that Juba’s labor market is characterized by survivalist employment, where work is informal, daily, and short-term. This finding corroborates AfDB’s (2022) report, where informal employment led employment numbers in fragile states. This study also identifies the resulting consequences of this trend, where, unlike in AfDB’s discussion of general employment, this type of employment forces a multiple approach to work, which leads to the fading of technical skills when they are not put to relevant practice. This finding aligns with Brunello & Wruuck's (2021) assertion that the period in which a skilled talent spends working in a field irrelevant to acquired skills would result in long-term unemployment risk.

5.5 Summary of Findings

The findings of this study lead us to a three-dimensional crisis that defines South Sudan's talent pipeline gap:

1. Educational: The system is heavily theoretical at the expense of hands-on learning. This reinforces the Skill Mismatch Theory.
2. Structural: There is no existing bridge from education to entry-level roles, e.g., there are no formal internships or apprenticeships. This aligns with (Walther & Frick, 2021) Findings.
3. Institutional: South Sudan lacks the infrastructure and tool capital that would support the capitalization of acquired skills to contribute to the national economy. This refines the Human Capital Theory.

Giotis (2024) argued that solving these problems requires a multifaceted approach that would create a circular ecosystem where education, government policy, and the private sector are in a constant feedback loop through a functional Labour Market Information System (LMIS).

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 The Proposed Integrated Talent Pipeline Model

To address the leaky pipe that was repeatedly identified in the analysis section of this research, this study proposed a circular ecosystem to address the implications of this study. As shown in Figure 12, the proposed model presents a feedback loop between the state, the labor market, and classroom input.

Figure 12: *The Integrated Talent Pipeline Model for South Sudan*

The proposed model is anchored on three pillars:

- **Sustainable Financing:** The proposal includes a 0.35% vocational training levy policy that will sustain the implementation of the digital hubs, ensuring that the solution does not rely on donor funding and foreign assistance.
- **The Internship Bridge:** Introducing mandatory academic internships into the curriculum, linked directly between academic institutions and the labor market, will solve the Experience Catch-22, equipping graduates with marketable experiences that entry-level employers seek.
- **Digital Modernization:** Through the introduction of community digital hubs, this model addresses the infrastructure barrier that many young people face. This feature of the model integrates digital inclusion for marginalized youth and allows them to transition

6.2 Strategic Recommendations

6.2.1 Summary of Recommendations

Table 6: *Summary of Strategic Recommendations for Enhancing the South Sudanese Talent Pipeline*

Stakeholder	Action	Expected Outcome
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Educational Institutions	Transition from a theory-heavy curriculum into a competency-based curriculum that integrates theoretical learning with practical assessments.	Strengthen graduates' ability to apply what they have learned in the real world by understanding and doing.
Educational Institutions	Making 3-month industrial attachments in the middle and end of the studies an institutionalized mandatory requirement for graduation, and tracking effectiveness and outcomes through monitoring and evaluation.	Enhance the employability of graduates and address the Experience Catch-22.
Private Sector & NGOs	Partner with academic institutions to establish academic internships that are aligned with market needs.	Expand talent pool, and move to merit-based hiring over close-ended/ referral hiring, hence creating equal entry-level pathways for youth employment.
Private Sector & NGOs	Form an advisory board that meets with academic partners annually to review and update training modules so they reflect labor market needs.	A curriculum that aligns with evolving industry needs and technologies, hence addressing the skills mismatch, and reducing costs on employee skill development.
Government & Policy Makers	Subsidize internet costs for initiatives promoting youth digitalization, and establish community digital hubs in Juba.	Reduce digital and technical skill deficits among youth across the country, leading to improved digital literacy rates.
Government & Policy Makers	Develop a national job portal where job seekers are matched with employers. Develop a national labor portal to match job seekers with employers.	Shift the system to merit-based hiring and address bottlenecks like nepotism and hidden opportunities.

Government & Policy Makers	Formulate and ensure the implementation of a 0.35% Vocational Training Levy on corporate revenue to build youth capacity.	A sustainable domestic funding for digital hubs and youth capacity building programs.
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6.2.2 Financial Plan and Funding Strategy

Table 7: Financial Plan and Funding Strategy

Initiative	Estimated Cost (USD)	Calculation Basis & Regional Grounding	Primary Funding Sources
National Labor Portal (LMIS)	\$50,000 - \$80,000	Estimated on Intermediate LMIS Based on "Intermediate LMIS" frameworks (FHI 360, 2023). Cater for MVP Software Development, a secure hosting platform, and a year-long data collection pilot.	MoL, World Bank, AfDB
Community Digital Hubs	\$80,000 - 100,000 per hub	100 edu-grade computers @ \$400, Solar: 5kVA system \$6,500. Connectivity: Starlink/Fiber install + data subscriptions \$4,000	UNDP, UNESCO, Private Sector CSR
TVET Curricula Modernization	\$30,000 - \$50,000	Hiring 3-5 professional industry consultants to revise the core curriculum to meet Competency-Based Education (CBET) standards.	MoGEI, International Partners
Subsidized Internships	\$500 - \$1,000\$ per intern/yr	Estimated basic needs stipend model in South Sudan covering meals and	Youth Funds, Private Sector

		public transport for in-person work days for 6–12 months.	
Vocational Training Levy (VTL)	0.35% Revenue Tax	Adapted from South Africa and Kenya’s Skills Development Levy (SDL) models of South Africa of 1%. The proposed 0.35% rate is lower, reflecting the fragility of South Sudan’s private sector, and is intended to encourage buy-in.	Policy Driven

6.2.3 Strategic Roadmap

To ensure these recommendations are feasible and executed successfully, this study proposes a chronological roadmap for the concerned stakeholders.

Phase 1: Short-Term (0–6 Months) – Foundation & Engagement

For phase one, a multi-stakeholder task force composed of the MoL, MoGEU, and private sector stakeholders will be established. A nationwide audit of existing government TVET systems will be conducted to assess what needs to be repaired, upgraded, or introduced. Once these are set in place, the internship program will be piloted with MOUs signed with partner startups and NGOs in Juba to create formal entry-level pathways.

Phase 2: Medium-Term (6–18 Months) – Implementation & Scale

Phase two will begin with the development and launch of the NLP and LMIS, which will play a key role in collecting market data. Within the same timeline, the modernization of the curriculum will be initiated to integrate digital, soft, and technical skills into vocational and post-secondary education modules. Digital hubs will also be set up, with at least three pilots in the city and metropolitan Juba. These hubs will provide free internet and devices to job seekers.

Phase 3: Long-Term (18+ Months) – Sustainability & Institutionalization

The third phase will begin after the implementation of short-term goals. This will involve the regional scaling of the Community Digital Hubs and Labor Portal beyond Juba and semi-urban areas to rural areas. This phase will also involve the implementation of the VTL and recognition of partner companies and startups that are hiring program graduates. This phase will also involve an annual review of the training outcomes and labor market landscape to ensure that they align with technological shifts.

6.2.4 Enhanced Implementation: The National Labor Portal

The NLP serves as a central hub where local talent is matched with demand. For effective implementation, the following steps should be taken.

Hosting and Management: The platform should be hosted and managed by the MoL and the Ministry of ICT. This would ensure that national labor data remains within the sovereign control of the state. The proposed solution should adopt various features to ensure inclusivity for youth with low internet access. This includes an SMS/USSD integration where a basic mobile interface can allow youth with non-smartphones to check job listings through USSD codes and job alerts via text. The NLP should provide employers with a verified talent database that reduces their recruitment costs. Businesses and companies that shift their hiring process to the talent portal will be eligible to receive tax waivers.

6.3 Limitations and Future Research

While this study has provided clear and actionable resolutions for addressing the skills mismatch across South Sudan, there are still limitations that invite further academic inquiry.

- **Geographic Scope:** This study focused exclusively on urban youth in Juba. Future research should expand the research area to other towns and rural states to compare how these findings compare across different geographies.
- **Employer Perspective:** This research mostly focuses on the experiences of youth. Future research should take a next step and provide an employer-side analysis, by collecting quantitative data from HR managers to validate and estimate the financial cost of retaining graduates and the detailed gaps in the alignment of education and their needs.

- Long-term Impact: To validate the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed interventions, future research should longitudinally track a graduate cohort over 18-24 months, measuring the correlation between internships, apprenticeships, and long-term income stability.

6.4 Conclusion

This study has comprehensively analyzed South Sudan's talent pipeline gap and its impact on youth employment. Through a multifaceted examination of the supply side, largely defined by theoretical academic systems, and the demand side, characterized by a pressing need for technically and digitally skilled talents, this study revealed structural factors that contribute to the skills mismatch that has subsequently hindered employment rates. The inconsistencies that were noted in the literature review on the effectiveness of the HCT in post-conflict and fragile zones have been addressed through a sequential explanatory mixed methods approach, which captured both the statistical gaps and the lived experiences of South Sudanese young job seekers.

The findings imply that these bottlenecks cannot be addressed through a one-size-fits-all approach. The findings point towards the need for a feedback-loop system where employers, training institutions, and the government communicate and are aligned. By implementing the proposed National Labor Portal and the Vocational Training Levy, South Sudan can improve the fragmented training system, creating sustainable education-to-employment pathways. This study serves as a strategic roadmap to equip youth with industry-relevant skills that will accelerate the achievement of the national development vision 2030.

6.5 Final Reflection

Addressing the bottlenecks in youth transition to formal work in South Sudan requires a fundamental shift from classroom volume to competency value. Building a sustainable circular ecosystem where education, government, and the private sector are well aligned will effectively address the leaky pipe obstacle. A successful implementation of this study's recommendations will transform this volume of graduates into an engine for national growth, economic sustainability, and a prosperous future for the Republic of South Sudan.

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